

Studies on the Membrane Conductance with a Millipore Filter Paper at different Temperatures in Presence of Alkali Chlorides and the Energetics of Ion Transportation by the Application of Absolute Reaction Rate Theory

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Conductance behaviour of a millipore membrane bathed in some common alkali metal chloride solutions at different concentrations has been studied at different temperatures. Membrane conductance values generally increase smoothly with increasing concentrations tending towards limiting values at higher concentrations. The order of magnitude of conductances within the membrane pores ($K^+ > NH_4^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$) is the reverse order of the hydrated sizes of these ions, as in the case of conductance of aqueous solutions. The Arrhenius activation energies (E_A) and also the activation thermodynamic parameters (ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger) and Eyring activation energy (E_E) have been calculated. The activation energies for conductance follow the order $E_{Li^+} > E_{Na^+} > E_{NH_4^+} > E_{K^+}$, and is quite consistent with the opposite order of the conductances, establishing that the hydrated ionic sizes are retained within the pores of the membrane and the greater the ionic size the higher is the activation energy required for conductance. For a particular electrolyte the energy values decrease with increasing concentration of the bathing electrolyte. The small negative ΔS^\ddagger values suggest that bond-breaking processes are not involved in the conduction process.

Transport processes across membranes are of great interest for biologists and technologists. Physico-chemical properties related to conductance and diffusion of simple salts through ion-exchange membranes were already studied a few decades ago¹. A group of workers have studied the diffusion and also the conductance phenomena with parchment^{2,4} and cellophane^{5,6} supported inorganic precipitate membranes, and sintered disc supported lipid, phospholipid⁷ and cholesterol⁸ membranes because these may mimic some properties of biomembranes in vivo. Some workers have utilised the concept of the absolute reaction rate theory⁹ as has been extended by Zwolinski *et al.*¹⁰ in the study of energetics of either the diffusion^{2,3,10,11} or the conductance phenomena^{4,11,12}, and tried to establish the relations between the structural, thermodynamic and kinetic parameters of the membranes, and also for the calculation of activation parameters. In all these investigations the membrane pores are

weakly charged and in some cases the pores are controlled by using the deposition of inorganic or organic substances.

Recently Samanta and Basu^{13,14} have studied the conductance of some common electrolytes through an 'uncharged' microporous membranes at different temperatures to calculate the various activation parameters using the concept of absolute reaction rate theory¹⁰, which are helpful in interpreting the mechanism of transport through the membranes. The aim of the present work is to extend the study of the conductance of some common alkali chlorides through the pores of one variety of a Millipore filter paper at different temperatures and also to calculate the energetics of transport through the membrane and the corresponding activation parameters utilising the same extended ideas of the absolute reaction rate theory^{4,10,11}.

Results and Discussion

The physical characteristics of the membrane are as follows : average pore radius, $0.45 \mu\text{m}$; membrane thickness, approximately $2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}$. The conductances were measured using solutions of KCl, NH_4Cl , NaCl and LiCl in the concentration range $0.1\text{--}200 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$ at suitable intervals. The temperature range studied was $298\text{--}323 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$ at intervals of 5 degrees.

The variations of specific conductance (κ) calculated from the measured conductances for different electrolytes at a particular temperature (298 K) rep-

Fig. 1. (A) Plots of specific membrane conductance κ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$) for different electrolytes against bathing concentration (mol m^{-3}) at 298 K, and (B) for KCl at different temperatures.

resented by Fig. 1(A) show that the membrane conductance for any cation increases with concentration having a tendency towards a limiting value at higher concentrations. The amount of increase in terms of percent value, depending on the electrolyte, reveals the interesting fact that the initial change is about 200 to 500% for a change in concentration from 0.1 to 1.0 mol m^{-3} (data not recorded). This comes down to 70 to 90% when the concentration changes from 50 to 100 mol m^{-3} , and finally in the concentration range of 100 to 200 mol m^{-3}

the increase is only about 6–7% (data not recorded) showing a limiting tendency at higher concentrations.

This limiting tendency of membrane conductance at higher concentration observed also by some earlier workers^{4,15,16} with their different types of 'charged' membranes and has been explained by them in the light of the competition between the membrane shrinkage producing higher resistance to the ionic paths and the greater salt uptake increasing the conductance values. The probable explanation for the attainment of limiting values in the 'uncharged' Millipore membranes may be given in the light of competition between two factors : with increase in bathing concentration the pores should be occupied by greater quantity of salt and this should increase the conductance, but because of expulsion of water from the pores of the membrane as the external bathing concentration increases the ionic mobility will decrease lowering the conductance. After a certain concentration the two factors may more or less balance each other, with the conductance tending towards the limiting values.

The conjecture of large water content within the membrane pores in the dilute range, and the exclusion of water at higher concentrations in case of 'uncharged' microporous membranes, has been verified experimentally earlier by Samanta and Basu¹³. The same test has been performed in case of the Millipore membranes (mentioned in the experimental portion) which also substantiates the idea of exclusion of water showing the initial increase and then decrease in the specific weights of the membrane with the increase in bathing concentrations.

The order of conductance values within the Millipore membrane is $\text{K}^+ > \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$, the same as in aqueous solutions¹⁷, suggesting that the ions retain their hydrated sizes, which is in the opposite order, within the pores of the membrane as in aqueous solutions. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that these conductance values are much higher than those found in the studies with the 'uncharged' microporous membrane¹³, obviously due to the fact that the average pore size of the Millipore

membrane ($r \approx 10^{-4}$ cm) is much larger than that in the microporous membrane ($r \approx 10^{-6}$ cm).

The temperature effect on the membrane conductance is shown with the electrolyte KCl in Fig. 1 (B). The general trend at any temperature is the same, showing an almost smooth increase with concentration tending towards a limiting value. The value at any particular concentration increases with increasing temperature. Exactly the same pattern has been found for all the different electrolytes studied here. The temperature variations of conductances of these electrolytes also maintain the same order : $K^+ > NH_4^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$, indicating that the opposite order of the hydrated sizes is retained even at the elevated temperature of 323 K. Since the swelling effect is negligible in these 'uncharged' membranes, the increase in conductance at elevated temperature is mainly because of the increase in ionic mobility within the pores, unlike greater salt uptake due to swelling effect as in the case of a 'charged' membrane.

The activation energies of ionic transport have been calculated by applying the simple Arrhenius equation⁹ in the form,

$$\kappa = A. \exp(-E_A/RT) \quad (1)$$

where κ is the specific conductance. The $\log \kappa$ values for any electrolyte at each concentration studied are plotted against $1/T$ to calculate the activation energy (E_A) from the slope. The smooth straight-lines for different electrolytes indicate that there are no irreversible structural changes within the membrane during the conductance measurement even upto the temperature 323 K.

Fig. 2 representing the plots of activation energies (E_A) of membrane conductance for different electrolytes against the concentrations, shows that the values are very high at low concentrations and decrease with increasing concentrations. The high activation energies at low concentrations indicate some kind of immobilisation of the ion within the pores, possibly due to absorption on the pore walls when it initially comes into contact with

Fig 2 Plots of Arrhenius activation energies (E_A) for different electrolytes against the respective concentration (mol m^{-3}) of the bathing electrolyte (axis not drawn to scale, shows only the respective values of the concentrations)

the electrolyte¹³, and this has been overcome as the concentration increases. The sequential order of activation energies, $E_{Li^+} > E_{Na^+} > E_{NH_4^+} > E_{K^+}$, quite consistent with the opposite order of conductance but of the same order as of hydrated size, further establishes that the greater the hydrated size, the greater is the activation energy required for ionic movement from one position to the other.

The absolute reaction rate theory extended by Zwolinski *et al.*¹⁰ and applied to conduction phenomena through membrane by various workers^{4, 12-14} has also been utilised here to study the energetics of ion conduction through the Millipore membrane, to calculate the corresponding activation parameters. The logarithmic form of Eyring equation correlating the membrane equivalent conductance with the enthalpy and entropy of activation on rearrangement stands as

$$\log (\Lambda h/kT) = -(\Delta H^*/2.303RT) + \Delta S^*/2.303R \quad (2)$$

where k and h are the Boltzmann and the Planck constants respectively. Excellent straight lines obtained by plotting $\log (\Lambda h/kT)$ against $1/T$ are utilised to calculate the values of ΔH^* from the slopes, and ΔS^* from equation (2) at a particular temperature

of 298 K. The corresponding activation energies of Eyring (E_E) have been calculated from the usual relation,

$$E_E = \Delta H^* + RT \quad (3)$$

The values of E_A , E_E , ΔH^* and ΔS^* are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I—CALCULATED VALUES OF ARRHENIUS (E_A) AND EYRING (E_E) ACTIVATION ENERGIES, ENTHALPY OF ACTIVATION (ΔH^*) AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION (ΔS^*) FOR THE CONDUCTION OF SOME COMMON ALKALI CHLORIDES THROUGH A MILLIPORE MEMBRANE AT 298 ± 0.1 K

Electrolyte	Concn mol m ⁻³	E_A kJ mol ⁻¹	E_E kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
KCl	0.1	44.8	44.6	42.1	-0.11
	1	12.4	12.3	9.9	-0.23
	10	11.6	11.1	8.6	-0.23
	50	8.6	8.5	6.0	-0.24
	100	7.3	7.2	4.7	-0.24
NH ₄ Cl	0.1	46.1	45.6	43.1	-0.11
	1	11.9	13.0	10.6	-0.22
	5	11.6	11.7	9.2	-0.23
	10	11.1	10.7	8.2	-0.23
	50	11.5	11.3	8.8	-0.23
100	8.3	9.8	7.4	-0.23	
NaCl	0.1	47.0	47.7	45.2	-0.10
	1	17.7	16.8	14.4	-0.21
	5	11.4	10.5	8.1	-0.23
	10	11.9	12.3	9.8	-0.23
	50	10.0	10.3	7.8	-0.24
100	9.3	9.3	6.8	-0.24	
LiCl	0.1	54.7	54.3	51.3	-0.10
	1	18.0	17.5	15.5	-0.22
	5	14.0	13.8	11.3	-0.24
	10	12.9	12.9	10.4	-0.23
	50	12.0	11.9	9.4	-0.23
100	10.6	10.5	8.0	-0.24	

The data show that E_E and E_A values are almost the same and maintain the same characteristics of decreasing pattern with increase in concentration. Moreover, the increasing trends E_E and ΔH^* from K^+ to Li^+ corroborate the idea that the greater the ionic hydrated size the greater are the activation energy and the enthalpy for conduction through this particular membrane. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that this sequence of activation parameters

is not in conformity with that found by some earlier workers with parchment supported precipitate membrane⁴, where the order follows the crystallographic radii, $E_{K^+} > E_{Na^+} > E_{Li^+}$, most probably because of the 'charged' and 'tight pores' of the membrane, where ionic dehydration^{18,19} is possible for the ions to get entry into the pores.

Fig 3 Cell for measurement of membrane conductance

The values of ΔS^* , which according to Zwolinski *et al.*¹⁰, indicate the mechanism of flow through the membranes, are shown in the last column of Table 1. The small negative values suggest that bond-breaking processes are not involved in this conduction process. On closer scrutiny it is found that for any particular electrolyte at very low concentration, ΔS^* value is relatively high, where the activation energy is also high. This suggests that possibly some 'depolymerisation' of water within the pores take place for which greater energy is required and entropy also increases due to greater disorderliness. The values of ΔS^* are almost the same for all the electrolytes indicating that no special immobilisation arises in case of any individual ion despite their differences in hydrated sizes.

Experimental

Millipore filter paper (gift samples from Millipore Filter Corporation, U.S.A.) attached between the two flanged ends of the half-cells of a U-tube with an adhesive like 'Quickfix', formed the cell as shown in Fig. 3. The method of conductance measurement was the one originally suggested by

Subrahmanyam and Lakshminarayanaiah²⁰ and used by recent workers^{4,10,12,-14,21}. The membrane pores were bathed in a solution of an electrolyte, maintaining a hydrostatic pressure difference of the solution on the two sides of the membrane, so that the solution may pass from one side to the other through the pores, allowing sufficient time with frequent renewal of the solution side which is constantly stirred with magnetic stirrer keeping the cell in the temperature-controlled bath (optimum time for equilibration has been standardised by performing the bathing process and measuring the steady values of conductance). The solution in the U-tube was then replaced by purified mercury without complete removal of the adhering surface liquid of the membrane so that no air layer remains at the mercury/membrane interface, and thus the membrane remained sandwiched between mercury on both sides. By inserting two platinum electrodes on the two sides and making electrical connections with the conductivity meter (Systronic 303), conductances (C) were measured at a frequency of 1 kHz. The specific conductance (κ) is calculated by using the formula, $\kappa = (1/a)C$, where l is the thickness of the membrane which separates the two mercury surfaces, and a the effective area of the membrane surface measured from the area of the opening of the flanged ends. Solutions were prepared with analytical grade KCl, NH₄Cl, NaCl and LiCl using conductivity water.

The change in the membrane content during bathing with external electrolyte concentration was measured as follows. A membrane of known weight in dry condition (W_D) was equilibrated with water and then successively with solutions of different concentrations of an electrolyte. The different weights of this wet membrane (W_S) were measured accurately with a microbalance after removing the adhering surface liquid only. The average of at least three weights in each case differing only by 0.5 mg, was used for the calculation of change in the specific weights with the relation, $(W_S - W_D)/W_D$. Temperature effects on the membrane content were studied similarly, keeping the membrane in contact with a particular solution in a thermostat at a desired temperature, and after removing the adhering

liquid, the membrane was kept in a closed weighing bottle and was weighed at room temperature.

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